

Epidemiological and histopathological aspects of lymphomas at Zinder National Hospital, Niger

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Abstract:

Introduction: Lymphoma is a malignant lymphocytic hemopathy characterized by diffuse lymph node or extranodal infiltration. It occurs at all ages and poses a problem for us in terms of positive diagnosis and management. The objective of this study is to determine the epidemiological and histological aspects of lymphomas at the National Hospital Zinder. **Methodology:** This was a retrospective cross-sectional study of patient records collected for histopathological examination between November 2019 and December 2023. Included were patients of any age and of both sexes with their histopathological findings available. **Results:** Lymphomas accounted for 3.47% of all malignancies. The 40 to 60 age group was

the most affected with 40.90% (n=9) of cases. The mean age was 45 ± 20.05 . The sex ratio was 1.75. Lymph node localization accounted for 68.18% (n=15) of cases. Histological examination confirmed the type of non-Hodgkin lymphoma in 77.27% (n=17) of cases. Phenotype B lymphoma predominates in 86.36% of cases (n=19). Our study showed that indolent lymphoma was the most common histological subtype of non-Hodgkin lymphoma in 31.82% (n=7) of cases. Hodgkin's lymphocytic depleted lymphoma was found in 13.63% (n=3) of cases. **Conclusion:** The analysis of these results allowed us to appreciate the extent of lymphomas and their multiple implications in our society by highlighting a high frequency of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas in the region.

Keywords: *Lymphoma, Cancer, Biopsy, Histology.*

Introduction

Cancer is a real public health problem for both developed and developing countries. Globally, it is the leading cause of death with 9.2 million cases in 2020 (Sung et al., 2021). Cancer of the lymphatic system or lymphoma is a malignant lymphoid hemopathy characterized by diffuse lymph node or extranodal infiltration (Alaggio et

al., 2022). It can be found at all ages. Lymphomas are a heterogeneous group of closely related diseases. There are two main types of cancers of the lymphatic system: Hodgkin's lymphoma (HL) and non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL) (INCa, 2016). Globally, the incidence of lymphoma has increased the most in recent years, with 13.3 cases per 100,000 men and 7.8 cases per 100,000 women. Thus, it is estimated

that approximately one million people are living with lymphoma worldwide today (Pages Jaunes, 2024). In 2018, the number of new cases of haematological malignancies (leukemia and lymphomas combined) is estimated at 45,000 (about 12% of cancers diagnosed), including 15,500 cases of lymphoma, the report says (Defosse et al., 2019). Lymphoma, the 6th most common cancer in France, its epidemiology in Africa is an ongoing research topic (Pages Jaunes, 2024). In Niger, it poses a real epidemiological, diagnostic and management problem. That's why we started this study on lymphomas. The objective of the present study is to determine the frequency, epidemiological profile and histological type of lymphomas in the Zinder region.

Materials and Methods

This is a cross-sectional study with retrospective data collection over a period of 50 months from 1 November 2019 to 31 December 2023 in the Clinical Haematology Department of the National Hospital Zinder. Study of the records of patients admitted for histopathological examination over a period of 36 months at the National Hospital of Zinder. Our study included all records of patients of all ages and sexes with available pathological findings. Epidemiological variables (frequency, age, sex, provenance, ILO population type: working-age population = labour force and inactive population and others = population under 15 years of age and population over 65 years of age) and diagnostic variables (biopsy, surgical specimen, primary tumour site and histological type) have been studied. The analysis and statistical analyses were carried out with Epi Info 7.2.2.2. Our results have been presented in tabular form. Microsoft Office 2016 Word and Excel were used for document entry and table design. The results are expressed as an average \pm standard deviation and as a percentage of individuals. We determined central tendency values for selected quantitative variables (mean, minimum, maximum, median).

Results

A total of 1598 patient records were included during the study period. This analysis shows a cancer frequency of around 39.61% (633/1598) on the set of samples taken. Lymphomas accounted for 3.47% (22/633) of all cancers. The 40 to 60 age group was the most affected with 40.90% (n=9) of cases. The mean age was 45 ± 20.05 with extremes of 8 and 70 years. The sex ratio was 1.75. The working population was the most affected with 17 cases, or 77.30%. The socio-economic aspects are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Patients by Socio-Demographic Aspects

Variables		n (%)
Age (years)	0-20	4 (18,20)
	20-40	6 (27,27)
	40-60	9 (40,90)
	60 et +	3 (13,63)
Sex	Masculine	14 (63,60)
	Feminine	8 (36,40)
Population Type	Working age	17 (77,30)
	Other	5 (22,70)

In 50% (n=11) of cases, the biopsy was performed. Lymph node localization accounted for 68.18% (n=15) of cases. Histological examination confirmed the type of non-Hodgkin lymphoma in 77.27% (n=17) of cases. Phenotype B lymphoma predominates in 86.36% of cases (n=19). The diagnostic aspects are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Distribution of Patients by Diagnostic Aspects

Variables		n (%)
Nature of the levy	Biopsy	11 (50,00)
	Operating room	11 (50,00)
Location	Lymph node	15 (68,18)
	Extranodal	7 (31,82)
Histological type	Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	17 (77,27)
	Hodgkin lymphoma	5 (22,73)
Phenotype Type	Phenotype B Lymphoma	19 (86,36)

	Phenotype T lymphoma	3 (13,64)
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Our study showed that indolent lymphoma was the most common histological subtype of non-Hodgkin lymphoma in 31.82% (n=7) of cases. Hodgkin's lymphocytic depleted lymphoma was found in 13.63% (n=3) of cases. The classification into different subtypes is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Distribution of Lymphomas by Histological Subtype

Variables		n (%)
Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	Diffuse large cell lymphoma	6 (27,30)
	Indolent B lymphoma	7 (31,82)
	T/NK lymphoma	3 (13,63)
	Burkitt's lymphoma	1 (4,54)
Hodgkin's lymphoma	Lymphocytic depleted Hodgkin's lymphoma	3 (13,63)
	Scleronodular Hodgkin's lymphoma	1 (4,54)
	Lymphocyte-rich Hodgkin's lymphoma	1 (4,54)

Discussion

A total of 1598 patient records were included during the study period. This analysis shows a cancer frequency of around 39.61% (633/1598) on the set of samples taken. Lymphomas accounted for 3.47% (22/633) of all cancers. This frequency is almost identical to the 3% reported in France according to national statistics with nearly 15,000 new cases each year (Defossez et al., 2019). This could be explained by the fact that globally, the incidence of lymphoma has increased the most in recent years. The 40 to 60 age group was the most affected with 40.90% (n=9) of cases. The mean age was 45 years \pm 20.05 years with extremes of 8 and 70 years. Our result was close to those of Kante et al. (2022) in Guinea, Fares et al. (2021) in Morocco and Zeggai et al. (2013) in Algeria in who reported a mean age of 43 years for non-Hodgkin lymphomas, 50 years \pm 20.47 years for lymphomas and 44.90 years for all types of

lymphomas combined, respectively. The sex ratio was 1.75 in our study. A study of lymphomas in southern Morocco found a sex ratio M/F = 1.03 (Fares et al., 2021). In a study carried out at the Oncology-Hematology Department of the Donka National Hospital in Guinea Conakry on the hospital prevalence of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, the sex ratio was 1.28 (Kante et al., 2022). In Algeria, a 2013 study on the histoepidemiological profile of lymphomas in adults in the west of the country found a sex ratio of 1.33 (Zeggai et al., 2013). We found a male predominance in these different studies. The working population was the most affected with 17 cases, or 77.30%. Hodgkin lymphoma is commonly diagnosed in adolescents, it can also be seen in older adults. Non-Hodgkin lymphomas can occur at any age (Vidal, 2016). In 50% (n=11) of cases, the biopsy was performed. Lymph node localization accounted for 68.18% (n=15) of cases. This result can be superimposed on that of Tolo et al (2022) who found in 2005 that superficial lymphadenopathy was the most common clinical sign. Fares et al. (2021) and Kante et al. (2022) had found superficial lymphadenopathy as the most encountered clinical signs in 70.5% and 75% of cases respectively. Histological examination confirmed the type of non-Hodgkin lymphoma in 77.27% (n=17) of cases. This result is slightly lower than that reported by French national statistics (Defossez et al., 2019). According to the report of these statistics, 85% of lymphomas are non-Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL). On the other hand, it is very close to that of Fares et al. (2021) who reported 80.1% of non-Hodgkin lymphomas. The predominance of phenotype B lymphoma was observed in 86.36% of cases (n=19) in our study. According to French national statistics, more than 80% (Defossez et al., 2019) of the lymphoma cases found were of type Fares et al. (2021) had found 64.4% of phenotype B. Lymphomas are phenotype B and therefore much more rarely phenotype. During our study period, indolent lymphoma was the most common histological subtype of non-Hodgkin lymphoma in 31.82% (n=7) of cases. Hodgkin's lymphoma with lymphocytic depletion was found in 13.63% (n=3) of cases. According to an Algerian study, large cell non-

Hodgkin lymphomas accounted for 28.6% (8). According to the 2022 WHO classification of lymphoid blood diseases, diffuse large B-cell lymphomas are by far the most common (Alaggio et al., 2022; Campo et al., 2022; Laurent et al., 2017). Scleronodular Hodgkin lymphoma was found in 51% of cases (Zeggai et al., 2013). There are histological variabilities in different regions of Africa. This survey allowed us to take stock of lymphomas in the Zinder region.

Conclusion

This study allows us to appreciate the extent of lymphomas and its multiple implications in our society. The first of its kind, it provides estimates of the frequency of lymphomas at the National Hospital in Zinder. The analysis of these results highlights a high frequency of non-Hodgkin lymphoma at the regional level. This overview of lymphomas will allow us to design studies that can determine the risk factors associated with lymphoma in the region and thus position the protocols in our current therapeutic strategy at the Zinder National Hospital.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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